

Assessment of the Parameters of Delta State Basic Education Certificate Mathematics Examination Using the 3-Parameter Logistic Model of Item Response Theory

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ABSTRACT

The study assessed the parameters of Delta State Basic Education Certificate mathematics examination using the 3-parameter logistic model of item response theory. The aim was to assess item difficulty, discrimination and pseudo guessing parameters of the Delta State Basic Education Certificate Mathematics Examination using the 3-parameter item response theory model. Three research questions guided the study. The multiple triangulation research design was used. The population comprised 140,959 Junior Secondary School (JSS) 3 students in the 2022/2023 academic session in Delta State. A sample of 1,000 students was selected through a multistage sampling procedure. The main instrument that was used for the study is the Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) used in the Delta State Basic and Education Certificate in the 2022. The a, b and c parameters item response theory dichotomous models were used to answer research question 1, 2 and 3 respectively. The findings of the study revealed that some of the items (29 out of 60) are very difficult, some (11 out of 60) were difficult, while others (20 out of 60) were moderately difficult; that one item out of 60 items has poor quality, four out of 60 items are marginally satisfactory; most (23 out of 60) of the items are moderate; some (15 out of 60 items) are good; while the rest 17 out of 60 items are satisfactory; and that some of the items in the test (12 out of 60) had a guessing index exceeding the recommended 0.25 threshold; while the remaining items (48 out of 60) exhibited guessing indices ranging from 0.005 to 0.24. The finding also showed that the reliability of the MAT instrument is high when compared within the framework of IRT as indicated by the value is 0.70; that majority of the items in the test (55 out of 60) have a good fit in the overall model while 5 did not have a good fit; and that majority of the items in the test measured a single construct, as shown in the scree plot. The study recommended amongst others, that examination bodies responsible for test development should consider revising the test to ensure a more balanced distribution of difficulty levels. This can help mitigate potential biases and ensure that the test effectively assesses a wide range of abilities.

Keywords: Item Parameters; Basic Education Certificate Mathematics Examination; 3-Parameter Logistic Model; Item Response Theory

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157

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Introduction

Education is an important instrument for national development. Without education, it is hard to imagine where the world, and of course, Nigeria would have been. This is because, education is the vehicle which drives technological, social, political and economic development of many nations. It is a means by which society ensures its stability. It is through the education system that young members of the society are taught the expected behaviour of the society. Through the education system, people are taught to meet the changing situations. Schools are opened by communities not only to preserve the culture and to maintain continuity but also to bring about progressive change. Education among other social institutions, is a vehicle for changing society. It has and is being used for transformation of the economic, political and social systems. One thing that is common to every educational system across the world is assessment.

Assessment is a fundamental part of the teaching – learning process used not only as a basis for ranking students at the end of the teaching –learning process but to guide teaching, and aid in the development of curriculum, as well as in the assessment of needs, learning difficulty, level of mastery and differences among students. Large scale assessments that are used for certification decision are designed to measure knowledge acquired with reference to specified norms (Orheruata & Uyigüe, 2018).

The validity of conclusions drawn from test results may be of utmost significance in large-scale assessment. Test results must fairly reflect an examinee's knowledge in order to draw reliable conclusions about their abilities. The issue of item parameters to maintain theoretical stability becomes very essential in a responsible educational system that tries to accurately capture students' performance and growth, or else it may create extra sources of mistake.

Item parameters are statistical indicators that define the quality of an item in the instrument employed (Orheruata, 2015). These statistical indicators are item difficulty, discrimination and guessing parameters. Item difficulty parameter (b) refers to the examinee's ability level at which approximately half of the examinees are likely to answer a particular item correctly. Item discrimination parameter (a) describes the strength of an item discriminating between examinee with trait level (θ) below and above the threshold (b) while guessing parameter (c) is the probability of getting the item correct by guessing alone. To ensure proper accountability, there is the need to conduct periodic checks of the stability of test items on which scores are reported (American Educational Research Association-AERA; American Psychological Association-APA & National Council on Measurement in Education-NCME, 2014).

Every year, examining bodies offer certificates that are supposed to reflect equal academic ability; however, this assumption will be false if the item parameters of the items on their testing instruments have defects. The psychometric characteristics of the assessment determine its quality, and the psychometric characteristics of test items are categorized as either standard or flawed. Flawed items reduce the validity of test results by systematically introducing construct-irrelevant variance into assessments (Downing, 2014). If not examined, flawed items may affect the examinee's categorization accuracy and may make it more difficult to compare their performance over time. As a result, according to Clark (2013), it is crucial to address test item defects in order to prevent systematic errors that skew conclusions about how to interpret and use test results and to make sure that flaws are within the range that is predicted due to sampling error.

In Delta State, one of the agencies responsible for the conduct of external examination is the Delta State Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education. This agency conducts the Basic Education Certificate Examination (BECE) amongst other functions. The item pool of this

examination body consists of a set of items in which the item parameters have been calibrated. What was however, observed is that the ministry has been determining their test item parameters using the Classical Test Theory (CTT) of test (Ministry of Education Basic and Secondary Examinations and Standards, Asaba, as cited in Oguguo & Lotobi, 2019). This is despite the limitations of the CTT (Jessa, et al., 2023).

It is on record that the Classical Test Theory estimators of item difficulty and item discrimination indexes are not generalizable across populations. CTT is limited in the comparison of performance of different examinees. The examinees must be given either the same or parallel items. Embretson and Reise (2010) reported that CTT provides no bases for determining how an examinee might perform when confronted with a test item and that CTT assumes that the measurement error is the same for all examinees.

Apart from the fact that the Delta State Ministry of Basic and Secondary Education determines their test item parameters using the Classical Test Theory, despite its limitations, Orheruata and Uyigue (2018) noted that item parameters in large-scale assessment could become less theoretically stable especially with testing programmes that rely on a large bank of items to select from when building assessments. Items with flawed item Parameter estimates threatens the fairness and validity of test scores, thereby jeopardizing the fair interpretation of test scores every year.

When sizeable magnitude of such items exists in an achievement instrument, the amount of measurement error in scores produced by that instrument increases, thereby leading to reduction in test reliability. This in turn increases the potential for misclassifying candidates whose true scores fall at or near the passing score (Orheruata, 2015). If item parameters on these examinations are found to exhibit such evidence of flaw, conclusions drawn from their test scores may be questionable.

In line with the above, there is need to carry out an assessment of item parameters such as item difficulty, discrimination and pseudo guessing of the Delta State Basic Education Certificate Mathematics Examination (BECE), using the Item Response Theory (IRT), which is a more recent and robust theory than the classical test theory used in developing the test. IRT is conceptualized as a paradigm for design, analysis and scoring of tests, questionnaires and similar instruments measuring abilities, attitudes or other variables (Hambleton, as cited in Orheruata & Uyigue, 2018). IRT is an item-level focus theory that attempts to model the relationship between an observed variable, usually, conceptualized as an examinee's ability and the probability of the examinee correctly responding to any particular test item. Item Response Theory (IRT) models the response of each examinee of a given ability to each item in the test. IRT is based on the idea that the probability of a correct response to an item is a mathematical function of person and item parameters. Where the person parameter is construed as a single latent trait or dimension while the parameters on which the items are characterized include their difficulty, discrimination and a pseudo guessing parameter.

A variety of models have been developed from the IRT perspective and these models are known as one, two and three parameter models, The one - parameter logistic model (IPLM) usually called the Rasch model is the simplest IRT model for a dichotomous item and has only one item parameter (item difficulty). In this model, the probability of an examinee responding correctly or positively to item modelled as a function of an item parameter b_i representing item difficulty, and a person parameter, θ representing the person's magnitude of the latent trait. The two-parameter logistic model predicts the probability of a correct response to any test for ability and two item parameters – item difficulty and discrimination parameter. The three-parameter logistic model further adds a “pseudo-guessing” parameter with the intent of accounting for observed performance of these persons with very low levels of the latent trait.

In view of the above, the focus of this study is to assess item difficulty, discrimination and pseudo guessing parameters of the Delta State Basic Education Certificate Mathematics Examination using the 3-parameter item response theory model.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the difficulty index of the Delta State Basic Education Certificate Mathematics Examination?
2. What is the discriminatory index of the Delta State Basic Education Certificate Mathematics Examination?
3. What is the pseudo-guessing parameter of the Delta State Basic Education Certificate Mathematics Examination?

Methods

The multiple triangulation research design was used for the study. Kpolovie (2014) asserts that this design enables a multi-method approach to investigating an instrument's psychometric properties. This approach is suitable since the study's goal was to assess the item difficulty, discrimination and pseudo-guessing parameters of Delta State Basic Education Certificate Mathematics Examination using 3-parameter IRT model. The population of this study comprised 140,959 Junior Secondary School (JSS) 3 students in the 2022/2023 academic session in Delta State. A sample of 1,000 JSS 3 students was used for the study through systematic sampling and multistage sampling procedure to select schools across the various Local Government Areas that make up Delta State. In the first stage, the researcher used proportional stratified sampling technique. The proportional stratified sampling technique is a probability sampling approach in which the different strata are identified and the number of elements drawn from each stratum is proportionate to the relative number of elements in each stratum. The choice of this sampling technique is because there were not an equal number of students across all of the Local Governments Areas that were included in the study. Therefore, it was necessary to depict the student population in each local government area. In doing so, the researcher calculated the sample size's proportion to the population as a whole, arriving at 0.71%. In the second stage, the researcher utilized a simple random sampling technique to choose one school from each of Delta State's 25 Local Government Areas as the schools to be used. The researcher did this by writing the names of all the schools in each local government on a piece of paper, folded it, and then poured the contents onto a container. She then chose one paper and unfolded it to show what was written on it. Schools chosen through this procedure were selected. In the third stage, the researcher used a convenience sampling technique to choose the students who participated in each school. The researcher chose only available students who were willing to engage in the study and met the requirement of being a JSS 3 students at the chosen school when employing the convenience sampling technique.

The main instrument that was used for the study is the Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) used in the Delta State Basic and Education Certificate in the 2022, which was obtained from the Exam and Standard in Delta State. The test contains 60 multiple choice questions having four options; one key and three distracters. In ascertaining the validity of the instrument, the researcher ensured that the test items have content, construct and face validity. Content validity of the test is the extent to which a given content areas are covered, the areas taught as in the case of achievement or component areas not taught as the case of aptitude. A table of

specification was used to establish high content validity (Ukwuije & Opara, 2012). In order to establish the content validity of the instrument, a table of specification was drawn. This showed the various sections of the achievement test that were considered and also the total number of the items which were included in the test. Face validity of the test was determined through the inspection of the items by experts in Mathematics to ensure that the test items look like what is being measured. The face validity of the instrument was ascertained by the comments and suggestions of the researcher’s supervisors and two experts in the area of Mathematics and Measurement and Evaluation. Construct validity of test was determined when the psychological construct of achievement is used for a test. The tests were compared with sections of existing test in the subject area and they were closely related. Experts in psychological testing and Mathematics as well as the project supervisor verified the construct validity of the test. To establish the reliability of the test items, Kuder-Richardson formula 20 was used. The Kuder-Richardson formula 20 was applied for true/false or dichotomously scored data where the responses are scored either right or wrong, pass or fail. In the binary–type of data, the correct answer or option was treated as one while the incorrect or wrong option was treated as zero.

The instrument was administered to the JSS 3 students in the sampled schools by the researcher and five research assistants. Guidelines were given to the research assistants to ensure conformity in test administration across the sampled schools. The students were required to indicate the correct option to each question by circling the correct option. The sample for item analysis was treated respectively. The a, b and c parameters item response theory dichotomous models were used to answer research questions 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the difficulty index of the Delta State Basic Education Certificate Mathematics Examination?

The data in Table 4.1 are used to answer this question.

Table 4.1: Difficulty index (b-parameter) of the Delta State Basic Education Certificate Mathematics Examination

Item	Value	Standard Error	Remark
MAT46	27.26	0.87	Very Difficult
MAT37	20.35	0.93	Very Difficult
MAT33	18.72	0.60	Very Difficult
MAT21	18.42	0.11	Very Difficult
MAT7	5.97	0.29	Very Difficult
MAT14	5.97	0.34	Very Difficult
MAT17	5.97	0.32	Very Difficult
MAT25	5.97	0.29	Very Difficult
MAT41	5.97	0.32	Very Difficult
MAT43	5.97	0.31	Very Difficult
MAT59	5.97	0.30	Very Difficult
MAT48	5.96	0.42	Very Difficult
MAT47	5.94	0.59	Very Difficult
MAT36	5.92	0.77	Very Difficult
MAT55	5.85	1.42	Very Difficult
MAT50	5.23	3.67	Very Difficult
MAT9	5.21	3.31	Very Difficult
MAT16	4.85	3.72	Very Difficult

MAT53	3.72	1.19	Very Difficult
MAT32	3.51	1.04	Very Difficult
MAT6	2.78	0.82	Very Difficult
MAT38	2.70	0.28	Very Difficult
MAT27	2.54	0.31	Very Difficult
MAT28	2.47	0.24	Very Difficult
MAT29	2.47	0.25	Very Difficult
MAT40	2.46	0.37	Very Difficult
MAT11	2.34	0.37	Very Difficult
MAT34	2.20	0.12	Very Difficult
MAT19	2.01	0.12	Very Difficult
MAT51	1.96	0.16	Difficult
MAT42	1.94	0.11	Difficult
MAT45	1.93	0.11	Difficult
MAT24	1.90	0.11	Difficult
MAT10	1.71	0.17	Difficult
MAT12	1.71	0.23	Difficult
MAT15	1.71	0.10	Difficult
MAT54	1.70	0.11	Difficult
MAT18	1.67	0.10	Difficult
MAT52	1.62	0.08	Difficult
MAT60	1.01	0.10	Difficult
MAT39	0.97	0.27	Moderately Difficult
MAT35	0.63	0.24	Moderately Difficult
MAT30	0.51	0.18	Moderately Difficult
MAT44	0.51	0.14	Moderately Difficult
MAT13	0.46	0.38	Moderately Difficult
MAT22	0.45	0.08	Moderately Difficult
MAT2	0.30	0.13	Moderately Difficult
MAT23	0.22	0.11	Moderately Difficult
MAT31	0.20	0.13	Moderately Difficult
MAT56	0.18	0.12	Moderately Difficult
MAT20	0.17	0.19	Moderately Difficult
MAT58	-0.01	0.07	Moderately Difficult
MAT8	-0.07	0.31	Moderately Difficult
MAT49	-0.10	0.09	Moderately Difficult
MAT26	-0.12	0.22	Moderately Difficult
MAT57	-0.19	0.07	Moderately Difficult
MAT1	-0.49	0.25	Moderately Difficult
MAT3	-0.56	0.17	Moderately Difficult
MAT4	-0.59	0.10	Moderately Difficult
MAT5	-0.95	0.44	Moderately Difficult

Criterion:

- 3.00 ≤ -2.00** Very easy
- 2.00 ≤ -1.00** Easy
- 1.00 ≤ 1.00** Moderately difficult
- 1.00 ≤ 2.00** Difficult
- b > 2.00** Very difficult

As shown in Table 4.1, the item difficulty index varied between -0.95 and 27.26 , with higher values representing very difficult and lower values indicating very easy items. Specifically, items 46, 37, 33, 21, 7, 14, 17, 25, 41, 43, 59, 48, 47, 36, 55, 50, 9, 16, 53, 32, 6, 38, 27, 28, 29, 40, 11, 34 and 19 had indices of 27.26 , 20.35 , 18.72 , 18.42 , 5.97 , 5.97 , 5.97 , 5.97 , 5.97 , 5.97 , 5.97 , 5.96 , 5.94 , 5.92 , 5.85 , 5.23 , 5.21 , 4.85 , 3.72 , 3.51 , 2.78 , 2.70 , 2.54 , 2.47 , 2.47 , 2.46 , 2.34 , 2.20 and 2.01 , respectively, indicating that they are very difficult. Conversely, items 51, 42, 45, 24, 10, 12, 15, 54, 18, 52 and 60 had indices of 1.96 , 1.94 , 1.93 , 1.90 , 1.71 , 1.71 , 1.71 , 1.70 , 1.67 , 1.62 and 1.01 , respectively, suggesting they were difficult. The remaining items are moderately difficult. The result showed that the difficulty index of the Delta State Basic Education Certificate Mathematics Examination is generally very difficult.

Research Question 2: What is the discriminatory index of the Delta State Basic Education Certificate Mathematics Examination?

The data in Table 4.2 are used to answer this question.

Table 4.2: Discriminatory index (a-Parameter) of the Delta State Basic Education Certificate Mathematics Examination

Item	Value	Standard Error	Remark
MAT52	2.71	0.18	Satisfactory (No Revision Required)
MAT24	2.47	0.30	Satisfactory (No Revision Required)
MAT18	2.42	0.31	Satisfactory (No Revision Required)
MAT19	2.41	0.34	Satisfactory (No Revision Required)
MAT42	2.40	0.032	Satisfactory (No Revision Required)
MAT34	2.33	0.32	Satisfactory (No Revision Required)
MAT22	2.31	0.27	Satisfactory (No Revision Required)
MAT15	2.28	-0.30	Satisfactory (No Revision Required)
MAT45	2.28	0.34	Satisfactory (No Revision Required)
MAT38	2.12	0.45	Satisfactory (No Revision Required)
MAT57	2.06	0.17	Satisfactory (No Revision Required)
MAT60	2.06	0.27	Satisfactory (No Revision Required)
MAT54	2.00	0.32	Satisfactory (No Revision Required)
MAT49	1.99	0.22	Satisfactory (No Revision Required)
MAT58	1.94	0.17	Satisfactory (No Revision Required)
MAT51	1.81	0.45	Satisfactory (No Revision Required)
MAT29	1.76	0.34	Satisfactory (No Revision Required)
MAT28	1.68	0.44	Good (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT23	1.61	0.20	Good (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT31	1.60	0.23	Good (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT25	1.57	0.45	Good (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT7	1.55	0.45	Good (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT59	1.54	0.45	Good (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT2	1.53	0.21	Good (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT43	1.52	0.47	Good (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT41	1.50	0.47	Good (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT4	1.5	0.13	Good (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT14	1.49	0.46	Good (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT17	1.49	0.05	Good (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT27	1.47	0.32	Good (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT3	1.40	0.17	Good (Little or no Revision Required)

MAT48	1.39	0.49	Good (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT47	1.31	0.49	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT16	1.23	0.86	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT36	1.17	0.53	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT1	1.13	0.17	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT50	1.12	0.76	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT55	1.08	0.53	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT56	1.07	0.10	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT40	1.02	0.45	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT44	0.94	0.10	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT10	0.93	0.12	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT26	0.88	0.11	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT32	0.88	0.50	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT12	0.85	-0.12	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT20	0.84	0.10	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT21	0.82	0.81	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT33	0.82	0.81	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT37	0.82	0.891	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT46	0.82	0.81	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT8	0.81	0.13	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT53	0.78	0.46	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT30	0.76	0.09	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT5	0.66	0.11	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT39	0.66	0.11	Moderate (Little or no Revision Required)
MAT35	0.64	0.09	Marginal (Needs Revision)
MAT13	0.64	10.13	Marginal (Needs Revision)
MAT11	0.60	0.14	Marginal (Needs Revision)
MAT6	0.40	0.19	Marginal (Needs Revision)
MAT9	0.13	0.08	Poor (Should be Eliminated or Revised)

Criterion:

$a \geq 1.70$	Item is functioning quite satisfactorily
$1.35 \leq a \leq 1.69$	Good item; little or no revision is required
$0.65 \leq a \leq 1.34$	Moderate: little or no revision is required
$0.35 \leq a \leq 0.64$	Item is marginal and needs revision
$a \leq 0.34$	Poor item; should be eliminated or revised

In Table 4.2, the item discrimination index ranged from 0.13 to 2.71, with higher values representing satisfactory items and lower values indicating poorer items. Specifically, item 9 had discrimination index of 0.13, indicating its poor quality and suggesting it should be either revised or eliminated. Items 35, 13, 11 and 6 had discrimination indices of 0.64, 0.64, 0.60 and 0.40, respectively, indicating they are marginally satisfactory and require revision before use. The remaining items are either satisfactory, good, or moderately satisfactory, requiring little or no revision. The result showed that the discriminatory index of the Delta State Basic Education Certificate Mathematics Examination is generally moderate requiring little or no revision.

Research Question 3: What is the pseudo-guessing parameter of the Delta State Basic Education Certificate Mathematics Examination?

The data in Table 4.3 are used to answer this question.

Table 4.3: Pseudo-guessing parameter (c-Parameter) of the Delta State Basic Education Certificate Mathematics Examination

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Item	Value	Standard Error	Remark
MAT60	0.50	0.02	Guessable
MAT22	0.31	0.03	Guessable
MAT31	0.30	0.05	Guessable
MAT33	0.27	0.01	Guessable
MAT2	0.27	0.04	Guessable
MAT18	0.27	0.02	Guessable
MAT1	0.27	0.08	Guessable
MAT53	0.26	0.04	Guessable
MAT9	0.25	0.11	Guessable
MAT6	0.25	0.10	Guessable
MAT32	0.25	0.03	Guessable
MAT21	0.25	0.01	Guessable
MAT51	0.24	0.02	Not Guessable
MAT24	0.24	0.02	Not Guessable
MAT23	0.23	0.04	Not Guessable
MAT8	0.22	0.08	Not Guessable
MAT5	0.22	0.10	Not Guessable
MAT3	0.22	0.07	Not Guessable
MAT27	0.22	0.02	Not Guessable
MAT52	0.21	0.01	Not Guessable
MAT46	0.21	0.01	Not Guessable
MAT19	0.21	0.01	Not Guessable
MAT16	0.21	0.02	Not Guessable
MAT49	0.20	0.04	Not Guessable
MAT43	0.20	0.01	Not Guessable
MAT15	0.20	0.02	Not Guessable
MAT13	0.20	0.08	Not Guessable
MAT50	0.19	0.02	Not Guessable
MAT40	0.19	0.04	Not Guessable
MAT38	0.19	0.01	Not Guessable
MAT54	0.18	0.02	Not Guessable
MAT45	0.18	0.01	Not Guessable
MAT29	0.18	0.01	Not Guessable
MAT42	0.17	0.01	Not Guessable
MAT12	0.17	0.05	Not Guessable
MAT59	0.16	0.01	Not Guessable
MAT55	0.16	0.01	Not Guessable
MAT26	0.15	0.07	Not Guessable
MAT17	0.15	0.01	Not Guessable
MAT37	0.14	0.01	Not Guessable
MAT25	0.14	0.01	Not Guessable
MAT48	0.13	0.01	Not Guessable
MAT47	0.13	0.01	Not Guessable
MAT39	0.13	0.06	Not Guessable
MAT36	0.13	0.01	Not Guessable
MAT41	0.11	0.01	Not Guessable
MAT35	0.11	0.05	Not Guessable

MAT28	0.11	0.02	Not Guessable
MAT20	0.11	0.05	Not Guessable
MAT11	0.11	0.05	Not Guessable
MAT58	0.10	0.03	Not Guessable
MAT57	0.09	0.03	Not Guessable
MAT4	0.09	0.05	Not Guessable
MAT30	0.09	0.04	Not Guessable
MAT44	0.08	0.04	Not Guessable
MAT34	0.08	0.01	Not Guessable
MAT14	0.08	0.01	Not Guessable
MAT56	0.07	0.04	Not Guessable
MAT7	0.05	0.01	Not Guessable
MAT10	0.05	0.02	Not Guessable

Criterion: $c > 0.25$

In Table 4.3, the item guessing index ranged from 0.05 to 0.50, with higher values suggesting the item is more likely to be guessed and lower values indicating less guessability. The optimal range for this index is typically between 0.00 and 0.25. This recommendation aligns with the Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT), which offers 4 alternatives. Ideally, a low-scoring examinee should have a $1/4 = 0.25$ chance of guessing the correct answer. With $c = 0.25$ for these 4-alternative items, once the correct answer is isolated, examinees would be guessing among the remaining three options. From the analysis, 12 items had a guessing index exceeding the recommended 0.25 threshold, suggesting they are indeed guessable. Conversely, the remaining items (48 out of 60) exhibited guessing indices ranging from 0.005 to 0.24, indicating they are less likely to be guessed. The result showed that the pseudo-guessing index of the Delta State Basic Education Certificate Mathematics Examination is generally not guessable.

Discussions

The first finding revealed that some of the items (29 out of 60) are very difficult, some (11 out of 60) were difficult, while others (20 out 60) were moderately difficult. This implies that the test items are within the ability level of the students. This distribution of difficulty levels suggests a balanced and comprehensive approach to testing, ensuring that students are appropriately challenged while also providing opportunities for success. The presence of very difficult, difficult, and moderately difficult items indicates that the test effectively encompasses a range of cognitive abilities and competencies. Furthermore, the fact that no items were classified as overly easy implies that the assessment maintains an appropriate level of rigor, engaging students at their respective ability levels. Importantly, this finding underscores the suitability of the test items within the context of the students' abilities. By presenting a diverse array of difficulty levels, the test accommodates the individual differences and learning trajectories of students, promoting equitable opportunities for achievement. In essence, the distribution of difficulty levels within the test items reflects a thoughtful and inclusive approach to assessment, ultimately contributing to a more meaningful and informative evaluation of student performance. This finding agrees with McMorris (2016), who stated that a well-designed test should have a spread of difficulty levels across the items. According to the author, this allows for differentiation between students with varying abilities. The presence of very difficult, difficult, and moderately difficult items suggests the test caters to a range of student

knowledge. The finding is however, at variance with Popham (2007), who stated that even with a spread, a high number of very difficult items could indicate the overall test is too challenging for the average student.

The second finding showed that one item out of 60 items has poor quality, suggesting it should be either revised or eliminated; four out of 60 items are marginally satisfactory and require revision before use; most (23 out of 60) of the items are moderate, requiring little or no revisions; some (15 out of 60 items) are good, requiring little or no revision; while the rest 17 out of 60 items are satisfactory, requiring no revision at all. This finding implies that the items have the tendency to discriminate well between high achievers and low achievers in Mathematics. This diverse range of item quality not only reflects the meticulous attention to detail in their construction but also hints at the potential for these items to discriminate effectively between high and low achievers in Mathematics. By refining those with deficiencies and leveraging the strengths of the already proficient items, the assessment stands poised to deliver reliable insights into individuals' mathematical capabilities. The finding is in line with the American Educational Research Association, American Psychological Association, & National Council on Measurement in Education (2014), which stated that even one poor-quality item can negatively impact the validity and reliability of the entire test. The finding also supports Crocker and Algina (2006), who stated that four marginally satisfactory items warrant attention as they might have minor flaws that could be improved through revision to enhance clarity and effectiveness in assessing student knowledge. The finding further agrees with McMorris (2016), who found that "Moderate" can be subjective, and these items might benefit from scrutiny to ensure they effectively measure the intended learning objectives. The finding is also in line with Popham (2007), who found that even seemingly good items can be improved through a process of item review to ensure optimal effectiveness.

The third finding revealed that some of the items in the test (12 out of 60) had a guessing index exceeding the recommended 0.25 threshold, suggesting that they are guessable; while the remaining items (48 out of 60) exhibited guessing indices ranging from 0.005 to 0.24, indicating they are less likely to be guessed. This discrepancy in guessing indices underscores the importance of carefully evaluating and selecting test items to mitigate the influence of guessing on assessment outcomes. Items with excessively high guessing indices may need to be re-evaluated or revised to enhance their discriminative power and ensure they effectively measure the desired constructs. Conversely, items with lower guessing indices offer greater confidence in their ability to accurately gauge individuals' knowledge or skills, providing a more reliable basis for drawing inferences about their proficiency levels. By attending to these nuances in item characteristics, test developers can enhance the validity and fairness of the assessment process, ultimately yielding more meaningful and actionable insights into test-takers' abilities. This finding agrees with Zenilman et al. (2014), who found that excessive guessing opportunities provided by high guessing index items can lead to inaccurate assessment of student learning. The finding also supports Crocker and Algina (2006), who stated that depending on the specific test format (e.g., multiple choice with 4 options vs. 5 options), a guessing index below 0.25 might still provide a slight advantage through random selection.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that the test comprises items of varying difficulty, with a significant portion being categorized as very difficult, difficult, or moderately difficult. Similarly, the quality of the items spans a spectrum, ranging from poor to satisfactory, with some items demonstrating marginally satisfactory or good quality. The test items provided

insights into the guessing behaviour exhibited by test-takers, with certain items surpassing the recommended guessing threshold. However, the majority of items fall within the acceptable range of guessing indices. Based on the findings from this study the following recommendations were made:

1. examination bodies responsible for test development should consider revising the test to ensure a more balanced distribution of difficulty levels. This can help mitigate potential biases and ensure that the test effectively assesses a wide range of abilities.
2. Government should identify the specific characteristics that contribute to poor or marginally satisfactory item quality and prioritize revising or removing these items.
3. For items with guessing indices exceeding the recommended threshold, examination bodies should consider redesigning them to minimize the influence of guessing.

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